

The Luna ecosystem: integrated tools for sleep signal visualization and analysis

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Summary

Sleep physiology generates rich, high-dimensional signals that are central to understanding brain function, aging, and disease, yet the field has long been constrained by proprietary data formats, closed-source algorithms, and a relative lack of open, scalable tools that support both large cohort analyses and detailed inspection of individual recordings. The Luna ecosystem is an open-source sleep analysis stack built around the Luna C/C++ library, its Python interface (`lunapi`), and Lunascope, an interactive desktop application for visualization, annotation, and review. Scripted and graphical workflows operate on a common data model and command set. Lunascope provides a synchronized multichannel viewer with hypnogram display, spectral summaries, annotation handling, automated sleep staging, cohort-level exploration, multiday actigraphy views, and direct access to the National Sleep Research Resource (NSRR). An embedded scripting console exposes Luna's command language inside the application, allowing users to move between visual inspection and programmatic analysis within a single session.

Statement of need

Computational analysis of polysomnographic (PSG) recordings has become central to sleep research. Large-scale datasets hosted by the NSRR have made thousands of

whole-night recordings freely available, enabling population-level studies of sleep architecture, spindle activity, slow oscillations, and EEG-derived biomarkers [1–3]. These analyses increasingly rely on open-source tools that can process recordings at scale, but many sleep researchers, clinicians, and trainees lack fluency with terminal-based or notebook-based workflows, and existing graphical tools for sleep data often emphasize either signal viewing or analysis rather than both within a reproducible open-source workflow.

The Luna/ `lunapi` /Lunascopes stack was developed to bridge this gap. Luna provides a reusable analytical core, `lunapi` makes that core available in Python for notebooks and batch workflows, and Lunascopes adds an interactive environment for review and exploratory analysis. This architecture supports both large-scale computation and detailed inspection of individual recordings within one analytical framework. Luna has been used as the primary analytic platform in studies analyzing over 10,000 PSG recordings across multiple cohorts in work by our group [1–5] and others [6–8]. Lunascopes brings those methods into an interactive graphical workflow.

Luna is also part of the broader US National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute NSRR [9,10] analytical ecosystem: in addition to sharing data, the NSRR has supported the use of common open-source tools for sleep research, and Luna has been used within NSRR analysis workflows. Lunascopes includes a Moonbeam module that imports NSRR data directly into the environment used for visualization, review, and downstream analysis.

Relationship to existing tools

Existing software relevant to PSG analysis reflects different design goals and usage contexts. EDFbrowser [11] is a mature and widely used viewer, well suited for manual signal inspection, but it is primarily a viewing application rather than an integrated sleep-analysis environment. Broader EEG ecosystems such as EEGLAB [12] and MNE-Python [13] are powerful and widely used, but they are general electrophysiology frameworks rather than dedicated PSG review environments. Sleep-focused research tools including YASA [14], Wonambi [15], SleepTrip [16], the Snooz Toolbox [17], and SleepEEGpy [18] support useful scripted workflows for staging, detection, preprocessing, or artifact cleaning, but they tend to emphasize individual pipelines or high-level wrapper layers rather than a shared analytical engine spanning command-line, Python, and interactive desktop review. Commercial PSG review systems support

clinical scoring and reporting, but are typically closed-source, proprietary, and difficult to adapt for reproducible research pipelines or large-scale open-data workflows.

Taken together, existing tools tend to separate signal viewing, algorithmic sleep analysis, and cohort-scale data exploration into different environments. This separation creates friction for reproducible research: visual review, scripted analysis, annotation management, and population-level summaries often occur in disconnected tools with different data assumptions. The Luna ecosystem was developed to reduce this separation by combining a scalable sleep-analysis engine, Python access through `lunapi`, an interactive desktop application for PSG review and annotation, cohort-level exploration tools, and direct workflows for NSRR-hosted data.

Many existing tools also concentrate on narrower task domains such as staging, visualization, or selected spindle, spectral, or preprocessing pipelines, whereas Luna spans a broader analytical range, including dataset manipulation with full support for gapped recordings; interval-level annotation handling; multi-day and actigraphy-based analyses; linear modeling; multivariate statistical approaches; neurobiological age prediction; high-density EEG support, including interpolation, connectivity, and EEG microstate analysis; and multiple spectral methods, including Welch, multitaper, wavelet, Hilbert, and IRASA-based analyses.

Software design

The software stack is organized in three layers. Luna, implemented in C/C++, provides the analysis engine and command set for sleep signal processing. It supports European Data Format (EDF/EDF+) inputs [19–21] together with XML and Luna annotation formats; the latter was designed as a simple tab-delimited representation that can accommodate clock-time or elapsed-time encodings, interval durations or change points, and associated metadata, making it relatively easy to import annotations from other domains. It also includes EDF manipulation and restructuring workflows, including support for generating EDF/EDF+ from ASCII TSV input. The native API exposes recordings and derived data as `Eigen` [22] arrays and matrices, evaluates the same domain-specific Luna scripting language used at the command line, and includes embedded command metadata that can be queried programmatically. Some time/frequency analyses and modeling components, including automated staging and related prediction workflows, build on external numerical libraries such as FFTW3 [23] and LightGBM [24]. Luna also supports association modeling, including linear-model and permutation-based inference implemented with efficient `Eigen`-based matrix

algebra. Figure 1 gives an overview of the core Luna tools, the scope of primary functions, and examples of the visual Lunascope interface.

Figure 1. Overview of the Luna & Lunascope. A. The family of Luna tools. B. Schematic of core domains of functionality in Luna. C. Visualization in Lunascope.

`lunapi` exposes that engine to Python, allowing the same recording objects and commands to be used in scripts, notebooks, and other applications. It supports single-recording and project-level workflows, including sample-list construction, command execution across cohorts, and structured retrieval of Luna result tables as Python objects.

Luna's output system is designed to separate computation from presentation. The same command outputs can be emitted to standard output, written to SQLite-backed [25] result stores that can be queried as virtual TSV-like tables, returned to Python as structured objects, consumed in R-facing workflows, displayed in Qt tables within Lunascope, or written as compressed text tables for larger results. Luna also retains a legacy R interface that, although not a primary distribution target, provides direct integration between R workflows and the Luna analysis environment. This output model helps preserve comparable results across command-line, scripted, and interactive settings.

Lunascope is implemented in Python (3.9–3.14) using PySide6 (Qt 6) and pyqtgraph as the graphical layer on top of `lunapi`, meaning every Luna command available at the command line is also available within the desktop application. A native desktop application was chosen over a web-based or Jupyter-embedded approach because PSG recordings are typically large (hundreds of megabytes), multi-channel, and require responsive pan/zoom interaction across hours of data. `lunapi` already provides a lighter-weight embedded viewer (`scope`) for JupyterLab; Lunascope is the more full-featured desktop environment within the same ecosystem.

The Lunascope interface is organized as synchronized docks around a central signal viewer. Docks can be shown, hidden, detached, repositioned, or tabbed, and the layout persists across launches. Several modules — including Moonbeam, the Explorer, and the Annotator — operate as floating windows. Full application state can be saved and restored via session files.

Within Lunascope, the viewer is tightly coupled to the Luna data model rather than operating as a passive display layer. Signals and annotations are attached through `lunapi`, can be inspected at multiple timescales, and can be queried or modified in the same session that executes Luna commands. Changes made in the visual annotation editor, for example, are immediately propagated back to the underlying Luna data model. Conversely, signals or annotations created or modified through Luna commands executed in the Lunascope console are immediately reflected in the viewer.

More generally, interval-level annotations are treated as first-class objects within Luna, and arbitrary expressions can be evaluated against those intervals, their metadata, and the underlying signals. For efficient navigation of long recordings, Lunascope maintains rendered, decimated signal caches and summary envelopes for broad time windows while preserving access to the underlying sample-level data. This supports interactive measurement, annotation-aware review, and direct visual inspection of outputs from Luna analyses.

Several interface elements are particularly important within the wider ecosystem. The embedded console executes native Luna command strings and returns structured result tables, so graphical and scripted analyses share one command language. The command browser and output tables use Luna's embedded documentation metadata to expose parameter and variable descriptions inside the application. Moonbeam provides direct access to NSRR studies and imports recordings into the analytic context used for interactive review. The Explorer extends the single-recording viewer to cohort-level displays, including hypnogram alignment (`Hypnoscope`), annotation summaries, waveform displays, and table-based plots. Lunascope also exposes stack-specific methods such as POPS and SOAP, multiday actigraphy views for EDF+D-style recordings, and rendered trace modulation by derived signal properties, allowing Luna outputs to be inspected as part of the visual workflow rather than only as exported tables.

In contrast, the command-line Luna tool is designed to support embarrassingly parallel workflows, including high-performance computing environments in which many recordings are processed independently. In that setting, per-job outputs can be written separately and later combined with Luna tools such as `destrat`, which compiles result tables across many files produced by distributed runs.

Research impact statement

The Luna/ `lunapi` /Lunascope stack supports a shared workflow spanning batch analysis, scripted exploration, and interactive review. Within the Purcell laboratory, Lunascope is used for PSG review, quality assessment, and exploratory analysis in projects that also rely on Luna's analytical pipeline, including work on sleep EEG spectral variation [2], neurodevelopmental sleep architecture [3], and the GRINS schizophrenia neurophysiology consortium [5,26,27]. This is particularly relevant for training and reproducibility because operations can be accessed through the command line, Python, and the desktop application.

Availability

The primary entry point for the Luna ecosystem is <https://zzz.nyspi.org/luna/>. Lunascope is distributed via PyPI [28] and as standalone macOS and Windows binaries built via GitHub Actions. The software is available at the Lunascope source repository [29], with user documentation available separately [30]. Luna documentation is available online [31], and includes extensive method-oriented documentation, worked examples and vignettes, and detailed descriptions of command options and outputs. Luna and `lunapi` are also distributed as Docker containers, and `lunapi` is accompanied by interactive notebooks and tutorials [32]. We have also developed an extensive six-part walkthrough [33], built around 20 hd-EEG recordings available through the NSRR Luna/GRINS dataset [34]. The Luna source repository is also publicly available [35].

AI usage disclosure

Generative AI tools (Claude, Anthropic and Codex, OpenAI) were used to assist in editing and formatting the text of this manuscript, and during software development, primarily to help refactor code, generate help-related functions and documentation, and assist with use of the Qt library in Lunascope. All content and code were reviewed, verified, and revised by the authors.

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